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* **Corresponding author.**

riviereassandi@gmail.com

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Effects of Lactic Acid Bacterial Strains on the Growth of Avian Pathogens: the Case of *Eimeria tenella*, *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli* APEC

Assandi Kouamé Rivière^{1*}, Sidibe Mamadou², Konan Kouadio Modeste¹, Bonny Aya Carole³

1 Laboratory of Biochemistry, Biotechnology and Food Sciences (LaBBSA), Science and Technology Training and Research Unit, Alassane OUATTARA University, BP V 1801, Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire

2 Central Veterinary Laboratory of Bingerville, Côte d'Ivoire

3 Laboratory of Biotechnology, Agriculture and Valorization of Biological Resources (LBAVRB), Biosciences Training and Research Unit, Félix Houphouët-Boigny University, Côte d'Ivoire

Abstract

Objectives: To evaluate the antibacterial and anticoccidial properties of lactic acid bacteria isolated from the digestive tract of quail. **Methods:** Two strains of lactic acid bacteria isolated from the digestive quail tract were used to test their antimicrobial potentialities against 3 avian pathogens. Antibacterial activity was assessed using the agar spot method on strains of *Escherichia coli* (APEC) and *Salmonella* inoculated into MRS agar. Anticoccidial activity against *Eimeria tenella* was assessed in liquid medium using MRS broth. Lactic acid bacteria were cultured for 48 hours in MRS broth, after which coccidia suspensions were added and the culture was incubated for 3, 4, and 5 days. **Findings:** The results showed that both strains were able to inhibit the growth of *Escherichia coli* (APEC) and *Salmonella*, with inhibition zone diameters between 13.5 ± 0.5 and 25.5 ± 0.5 mm. The results of the anticoccidial activity show that the strains reduce the proliferation of coccidia up to a rate of 81% in the medium, after 5 days of incubation. **Novelty:** Lactic acid bacteria produce antibacterial and anticoccidial compounds during their growth.

Keywords: Antibacterial activity; Anticoccidial activity; *Escherichia coli* (APEC); *Salmonella*; *Eimeria tenella*; lactic bacteria

1 Introduction

Lactic acid bacteria are attracting increasing interest as natural alternatives to antibiotics, in a context where bacterial resistance poses a major threat to global public health. The misuse and overuse of antibiotics, both in human medicine and agriculture, have fostered the emergence of multidrug-resistant bacterial strains, making some infections increasingly difficult, or even impossible, to treat⁽¹⁾. Avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (APEC), *Salmonella*, and coccidia (*Eimeria tenella*) are microorganisms responsible for disease in poultry farming and are increasingly resistant to antibiotics⁽²⁾.

APEC is a serious threat to poultry businesses worldwide, generating infections such as colibacillosis, which can result in huge economic losses⁽³⁾. Coccidiosis adversely causes high mortality rates, negatively affects growth and feed utilization, and increases the susceptibility of birds to subsequent diseases⁽⁴⁾.

The 2 main approaches used in commercial chicken production to manage coccidiosis and bacterial infection are chemoprophylaxis, which is mostly applied to broiler chicks, and immunization with live, virulent, or attenuated oocysts (egg-laying chickens)⁽⁵⁾. Drug administration has been a successful control technique for a long time. Still, as drug resistance increases, there is a need to offer drug-free products and decrease their use in animal production⁽⁶⁾.

Advances in food preservation technology have significantly improved human life. Natural biopreservatives are in extensive consumer demand⁽⁷⁾. Bacteriocins research has expanded into the discovery of novel antimicrobial compounds capable of combating pathogens. Bacteriocins are one of the substances synthesized by lactic acid bacteria during their growth⁽⁸⁾. Examples of metabolites produced by lactic acid bacteria include organic acids, diacetyl, hydrogen peroxide, and bacteriocins, or antimicrobial proteins⁽⁷⁾. Lactic acid bacteria represent promising elements for a new approach to controlling pathogenic microorganisms.

Lactic acid bacteria have the ability to inhibit a broad spectrum of microorganisms, including protozoa, fungi, yeasts, and bacteria⁽⁹⁾. Their antibacterial activity is an important characteristic in the characterization of probiotics because they contribute to the elimination of undesirable bacteria by colonizing the host, thus helping to prevent the proliferation of pathogens in the host⁽¹⁰⁾. They have a wide range of potential applications, including detoxification through adsorption and biotransformation of toxins, nutrient uptake in plants, strengthening plant resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses, and inhibiting agricultural pathogens through the production of antimicrobial molecules⁽¹¹⁾.

Lactic acid bacteria are microorganisms widely distributed in various natural ecosystems, ranging from fermented food products to aquatic and terrestrial environments, including the digestive tract of humans and animals⁽¹²⁾. This wide distribution reflects their adaptability and functional diversity, thanks to their production of bioactive metabolites such as organic acids⁽¹³⁾. Lactic acid bacteria are attracting increasing interest, particularly in light of rising antibiotic resistance. Hence the importance of leveraging technological advances to identify new strains with effective antimicrobial activity, especially against infectious agents⁽¹⁴⁾.

The objective of this work is to evaluate the antibacterial and anticoccidial properties of inhibitory substances from strains of lactic acid bacteria isolated from the digestive tract of quail.

2 Methodology

Two strains of lactic acid bacteria were used in this study. They were isolated from the digestive tract of quail by⁽¹⁵⁾. The antibacterial activity of the lactic acid bacteria isolates was demonstrated by direct action against multidrug-resistant strains, namely *Salmonella enterica* serogroup O:8 and *Escherichia coli* from the Bingerville Central Veterinary Laboratory (LCVB). The antagonistic effect of lactic acid bacteria strains against pathogenic strains was performed in bulk as described by⁽⁹⁾. 24-hour cultures of the pathogenic *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* strains were suspended in sterile distilled water at a loading of 10 CFU/ml, equivalent to a turbidity control of 0.5 McFarland. This suspension was then diluted 1:10 in supercooled MRS agar (45°C). After the agar solidified in Petri dishes, 24-hour lactic acid bacteria isolates were spot-inoculated at a rate of 5 colonies per spot. The Petri dishes were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Antibacterial activity is characterized by the appearance of zones of inhibition (clear areas) around the spots. The two lactic acid bacteria strains were also used for the *in vitro* study of anticoccidial activity against *Eimeria tenella*. The parasite population is inhibited by the action of inhibitory substances released by the lactic acid bacteria isolates during their growth. The *in vitro* anticoccidial activity of the lactic acid bacteria against *Eimeria* sp was studied according to the methods described in⁽¹⁶⁾. The lactic acid bacteria strains were cultured in 8 ml of MRS broth (Difco, USA) at a ratio of 1:10 and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. A negative control tube, a positive control tube, and test tubes for each lactic acid bacteria strain were prepared. In the negative control tube, 1 ml of coccidia suspension was added to 9 ml of MRS broth. The negative control tube contained only coccidia in MRS broth. For the positive control tube, 1 ml of coccidia suspension and 1 ml of a solution containing an anticoccidial agent dissolved in sterile distilled water (Amprolium at a concentration of 2 mg/ml) were added to a tube containing 8 ml of MRS broth. Thus, the positive control tube contained both coccidia and Amprolium. For the test tubes, for each strain used, 1 ml of coccidia suspension and 1 ml of MRS broth were added to 8 ml of a 48-hour preculture. Each test tube then contained both lactic acid bacteria and coccidia. The negative and positive control tubes, as well as the test tubes, were incubated for 72h, 96h, and 120h. For each tube, the coccidia concentration was 4.16×10^3 oocysts/ml. Each test was performed in triplicate.

Coccidia suspensions were obtained from broiler chicken fecal samples. The number of oocysts in each tube was determined before and after testing by the McMaster method as performed by⁽¹⁷⁾. Fecal samples from poultry were collected and then

analyzed. The analysis was carried out according to the Mac MASTER coccidia counting method. Thus, 3 grams of fecal samples were homogenized in a mortar with 42 mL of sterile distilled water. The resulting mixture was poured through a tea strainer. Then the filtrate was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. Each collected base was suspended in 20 mL of 40% (w/v) sodium chloride (NaCl) solution. Using a pipette, 0.20 mL of this suspension was taken and then introduced into a Mac MASTER cell. Then, observation under an optical microscope with an X10 objective revealed the presence or absence of parasite eggs in the cells of Mac MASTER. For the culture of lactic acid bacteria and coccidia, 5 ml of culture broth was diluted in 5 ml of an 80% NaCl solution to obtain a 40% NaCl solution. Using a pipette, 0.20 mL of this suspension was taken and then introduced into a Mac MASTER cell. Then, observation under an optical microscope with an X10 objective revealed the presence or absence of parasite eggs in the cells of Mac MASTER.

Antibacterial activity data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Results are expressed as the oocyst reduction rate. Data were subjected to analysis of variance using Turkey's test. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0 with a significance level of 5% ($p < 0.05$).

3 Results and discussion

The study of the antibacterial activity of lactic acid bacteria, performed using the spot method on *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* strains, demonstrated their ability to inhibit pathogen growth. Inhibition of pathogen growth is characterized by the appearance of clear inhibition zones around the lactic acid bacteria spots (Figure 1). The two lactic acid bacteria strains tested impacted pathogen growth by producing inhibition zones of different diameters. The strains were coded BL1 and BL2. Strain BL1 showed diameters of 25.5 ± 0.5 mm and 13.5 ± 0.5 mm against *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* strains, respectively. Against *Salmonella* strains, strain BL2 exhibited an inhibition diameter of 15.5 ± 0.5 mm, and against *Escherichia coli* strains, the observed inhibition diameter was 19.5 ± 1 mm (Table 1).

Fig 1. Expression of inhibition by the appearance of inhibition zones

Table 1. Inhibition diameters of isolated lactic acid bacteria

Code	Fermentation type	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Salmonella</i>
BL1	Bacillus/Heterofermentative	25.5 ± 0.5	13.5 ± 0.5
BL2	Bacillus/Heterofermentative	19.5 ± 1	15.5 ± 0.5

Inhibition of *Escherichia coli* growth was observed in this study. The results of Nguyen et al.⁽¹⁸⁾, focusing on the probiotic role of lactic acid bacteria, highlight those strains such as *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* produce bioactive

peptides, lactic acid, or lectins capable of strongly inhibiting the adhesion, virulence, and growth of pathogenic *Escherichia coli*, almost completely suppressing their development while promoting the proliferation of lactic acid bacteria. Tawab et al. (19) also report antibacterial activity of lactic acid bacteria isolates against pathogenic bacterial strains, including *Salmonella enterica*, with inhibition zones of up to 20 mm in diameter. Lactic acid bacteria isolated from the digestive tract of wild boar have also shown inhibitory activity against *Escherichia coli* strains, *Salmonella* Typhimurium, and *Staphylococcus aureus* by the agar diffusion method, with inhibition zone diameters ranging from 12 to 19 mm (3). Tian et al. (20) also report the *in vitro* antibacterial potential of lactic acid bacteria against strains of *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*, with inhibition zone diameters ranging from 11 to 24 mm across all strains. In addition to the bacterial pathogens *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli*, other studies highlight targeted activity against resistant strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Pseudomonas damnosus* (21) (22).

A substantial body of evidence suggests that several probiotic bacteria can exert antagonistic activity against pathogenic gut microbes. While considerable attention has been paid to the spread of antibiotic resistance, antimicrobial activity against pathogenic microbes has been a significant concern (19). Several studies have been conducted to date to describe the potential application of probiotic bacteria and their by-products to combat pathogenic bacteria in the food environment (23).

The viability of coccidial oocysts was assessed by counting them after 72, 96, and 120 hours of incubation at 25°C in contact with the different treatments. The results showed that the number of *Eimeria tenella* oocysts was reduced by both strains of lactic acid bacteria, and the reduction was greater after 120 hours of incubation.

The results indicate that the most toxic or coccidiocidal treatment after 120 hours of incubation was that of the BL2 strain. From 72 hours of incubation, 81% of oocysts survived, and the survival rate increased to 66% on day 4 before falling to 19% on day 5. The BL1 strain was more coccidiocidal on day 3 compared to the BL2 strain. However, the survival rate remained unchanged on day 4. On day 5, the survival rate was 30% compared to the negative control. With Amprolium (a synthetic anticoccidial), the survival rate was 22% on day 3 of incubation and then 7% on days 4 and 5 of incubation (Figure 2). Against protozoa, including *Eimeria tenella*, lactic acid bacteria have the ability to reduce the number of oocysts. Very few studies have demonstrated the *in vitro* anticoccidial activity of lactic acid bacteria. However, lactic acid bacteria have been the subject of *in vivo* experiments. Włosek et al. (24) reported, based on an experiment involving lactic acid bacteria supplementation in chicken farming, a reduction in the number of *Eimeria tenella* oocysts. The effect of probiotic supplementation was observed as early as day 7 of the experiment. Javanmiri et al. (25), in their studies, also demonstrated the ability of probiotic lactic acid bacteria to moderate the *in vivo* oocyst count, similar to that achieved by a synthetic anticoccidial. Furthermore, subjects exposed to lactic acid bacteria showed reduced lesions caused by the *Eimeria tenella* parasite.

Fig 2. Survival rate of coccidia in the presence of lactic acid bacteria

4 Conclusion

The present work aimed to evaluate the antibacterial and anticoccidial properties of lactic acid bacteria strains isolated from the digestive tract of quail on strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* and the parasite *Eimeria tenella*.

Using two strains of lactic acid bacteria isolated from the digestive tract of quail, antibacterial activity as measured by the spot method demonstrated an antibacterial effect characterized by the inhibition of bacterial growth. This inhibition was manifested by an absence of growth around spots ranging from 19.5 to 25.5 mm in diameter on the *E. coli* layer. With the *Salmonella* strain, the diameters ranged from 13.5 to 15.5 mm. These strains were also tested against the parasite *Eimeria tenella* for their anticoccidial potential. This potential was demonstrated by co-culturing lactic acid bacteria and coccidia. The results showed that, in the same medium, the coccidia reduction rate reached 81% after 5 days.

These results indicate that lactic acid bacteria isolated from the quail digestive tract produce antimicrobial compounds, particularly antibacterial and antiparasitic compounds, during their growth. In the future, this work could guide the isolation of compounds produced by lactic acid bacteria and the evaluation of their individual potential against avian pathogens in the search for new antimicrobial compounds.

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References

- Ohaegbu CG, Anayochukwu C, Ngen ODC, Chidiebere F, Uchechukwu, Ihuoma N. Characterization and antibacterial activity of lactic acid bacteria isolated from traditionally fermented foods against some selected food pathogens. *Journal of Advances in Microbiology*. 2022;22(10):15–24. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jamb/2022/v22i1030500>.
- Assandi KR, Toure A, Bonny AC, Karou TG. Prospects for the use of medicinal plant extracts (*Mallotus oppositifolius* and *Kalanchoe crenata*) as antimicrobials against salmonellosis in poultry. *Online Journal of Animal and Feed Research*. 2024;14(4):243–251. <https://dx.doi.org/10.51227/ojaf.2024.29>.
- Li Q, Yin L, Xue M, Wang Z, Song X, Shao Y, et al. The transcriptional regulator PhoP mediates the tolC molecular mechanism on APEC biofilm formation and pathogenicity. *Avian Pathology*. 2020;9(3):211–220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03079457.2019.1701182>.
- Liao S, Lin X, Zho Q, Wang Z, Yan Z, Wang D, et al. Epidemiological investigation of coccidiosis and associated risk factors in broiler chickens immunized with live anticoccidia vaccines in China. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*. 2024;11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2024.1375026>.
- Soutter F, Werling D, Tomley FM, Blake DP. Poultry coccidiosis: Design and interpretation of vaccine studies. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*. 2020;7:101–113. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.00101>.
- Nahed A, El-Shall, El-Naggar K, Ghadeer M, Albadrani, Nagwa I, et al. The anticoccidial effects of probiotics and prebiotics on the live coccidia vaccine and the subsequent influence on poultry performance post-challenge with mixed *Eimeria* species. *Poultry Science*. 2024;103:104283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.104283>.
- Amiri S, Moganjougi ZM, Bari MR, Khaneghah AM. Natural protective agents and their applications as bio-preservatives in the food industry: An overview of current and future applications. *Italian Journal of Food Science*. 2021;33(SP1):68–55. <https://doi.org/10.15586/ijfs.v33iSP1.2045>.
- Canon F, Nidelet T, Guédon E, Thierry A, Gagnaire V. Understanding the mechanisms of positive microbial interactions that benefit lactic acid bacteria co-cultures. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 2020;11:2088. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.02088>.
- N'Guessan YD, Bonny AC, Aké MDF, Assandi KR, Koffi DM. Study of the probiotic potentialities of lactic acid bacteria isolated from maize (*Zea mays*) in Côte d'Ivoire. *International Journal of Biosciences*. 2022;20(6):32–44. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/20.6.32-44>.
- Zapašnik A, Sokolowska B, Bryła M. Role of lactic acid bacteria in food preservation and safety. *Foods*. 2022;11(9):1283. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11091283>.
- Chen X, Bai H, Mo W, Zheng X, Chen H, Yin Y, et al. Lactic acid bacteria bacteriocins: Safe and effective antimicrobial agents. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2025;26(9):4124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26094124>.
- Maky MA, Ishibashi N, Gong X, Sonomoto K, Zendo T. Distribution of bacteriocin-like substance-producing lactic acid bacteria in Egyptian sources. *Applied Microbiology*. 2025;5(1):20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/applmicrobiol5010020>.
- López-García E, Benítez-Cabello A, Vilches N, Garrido-Fernández A, Arranz VM, Arroyo-López FN. Delving into the study of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts distribution in table olive biofilms using a non-destructive procedure. *Food Microbiology*. 2023;113:104250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2023.104250>.
- Raman J, Kim JS, Choi KR, Eun H, Yang D, Ko YJ, et al. Application of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) in sustainable agriculture: Advantages and limitations. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2022;23(14):77–84. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23147784>.
- Bonny AC, Aké MDF, Assandi KR, Karou TG. Inhibitory potentialities of lactic acid bacteria isolated from quail caeca (*Cortunix cortunix japonica*) on the growth of antibiotic resistant pathogens in Côte d'Ivoire. *International Journal of Biology Sciences*. 2022;4(1):01–08. <https://doi.org/10.33545/26649926.2022.v4.i1a.34>.
- Remmal A, Achahbar S, Bouddine L, Chami N, Chami F. In vitro destruction of *Eimeria* oocysts by essential oils. *Veterinary Parasitology*. 2011;182(2-4):121–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2011.06.002>.
- Bonny AC, Assandi KR, Ake MDF, Koffi KS. Impact of plant extracts on zootechnical, microbiological and biochemical parameters of broiler chicken of the Cobbs 500 breed (*Gallus gallus domesticus*). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Science*. 2025;14(08):1–9. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2025.1408.001>.
- Nguyen PT, Nguyen TT, Bui DC, Hong PT, Hoang QK, Nguyen HT. Exopolysaccharide production by lactic acid bacteria: The manipulation of environmental stresses for industrial applications. *AIMS Microbiology*. 2020;6(4):451–469. <https://doi.org/10.3934/MICROBIOL.2020027>.
- Tawab FIA, Elkadr MHA, Sultan AM. Probiotic potentials of lactic acid bacteria isolated from Egyptian fermented food. *Scientific Reports*. 2023;13:16601. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-43752-0>.
- Tian C, Wang L, Liu M, Liu J, Qiu M, Chen Y. Isolation and identification of chicken-derived lactic acid bacteria: In vitro probiotic properties and antagonistic effects against *Salmonella pullorum*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Escherichia coli*. *Microorganisms*. 2024;12:795.

- <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms12040795>.
- 21) Kiani A, Nami Y, Hedayati S, Komi DEA, Goudarzi F, Haghshenas B. Application of Tarkhineh fermented product to produce potato chips with strong probiotic properties, high shelf-life, and desirable sensory characteristics. *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 2021;12:657579. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.657579>.
 - 22) Mahsa S, Bahman P, Atefeh M, Mohammad AH, Daniel EAK, Yousef N. Screening of potential probiotic lactic acid bacteria with antimicrobial properties and selection of superior bacteria for application as biocontrol using machine learning models. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*. 2022;162:113471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2022.113471>.
 - 23) Mgomi FC, ran Yang Y, Gen C, Zhen-quan Y. Lactic acid bacteria biofilms and their antimicrobial potential against pathogenic microorganisms. *Biofilm*. 2023;5:100118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioflm.2023.100118>.
 - 24) Arczewska-Włosek A, Świątkiewicz S, Ognik K, Józefiak D. Effects of a dietary multi-strain probiotic and vaccination with a live anticoccidial vaccine on growth performance and haematological, biochemical and redox status indicators of broiler chickens. *Animals*. 2022;12(24):3489. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani12243489>.
 - 25) Javanmiri G, Rahimi S, Torshizi MAK, Nabiyan S, Behnamifar A, Grimes J. Comparison of the effect of anticoccidial drug, probiotic, synbiotic, phytochemicals and vaccine in prevention and control of coccidiosis in broiler chickens challenged with *Eimeria* spp. *Poultry Science*. 2024;103(12):104357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.104357>.